

Huang-Lao Daoism

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Huang-Lao Daoism 黄老道 was the dominant tradition of Daoism throughout the Han Dynasty. Although concrete historical records that would allow us to clearly document its origins are less than concrete, its first and formative phase began in the middle period of the Warring States, as evidenced in the earliest of its known writings, including the excavated texts Hengxian 恒先 and Fanwu liuxing 凡物流形 that are dated to that time. These texts reveal that the tradition was inspired by the philosophy of the Daodejing 道德经, commonly attributed to the ancient sage Laozi 老子; it represents the foundational text of Daoism that had already been in circulation from at least the early Warring States and that is identified with an earlier tradition of Daoism sometimes called Yangsheng Daoism 養生道. As demonstrated by these excavated Huang-Lao texts, the burgeoning Huang-Lao tradition had appropriated Laozi's earlier version of the Daodejing that is reflected in the excavated Guodian Laozi 郭店老子 together with its philosophical thought and altered it in significant ways to make it conform to their own different perspectives, primarily concerning cosmology and government. Whereas the core features of Laozi's original Daodejing centered on a phenomenology of the Dao, the figure of the sage, and the cultivational practice of yangsheng 養生 ("feeding life"), the core features of the Huang-Lao version of the text centered on a metaphysics of the Dao, the mysticism of the sage-ruler, and the practice of mental concentration often called zuowang 坐忘 ("sit and forget") that was championed by other texts of the period, namely the Neiye 内业 and the Zhuangzi 莊子. Huang-Lao thought thus emphasized a hierarchical vision of the cosmos in conjunction with an autocratic vision of ideal government in the hands of the enlightened sage-ruler who enjoyed a privileged relationship with the Dao. The second phase of Huang-Lao spans from the last period of the Warring States to the end of the Qin Dynasty, during which the tradition developed to such an extent that their thought was given ample recognition next to Confucianism, Legalism, and the other major schools of early Chinese philosophical debate in the major philosophical compendiums of the period, namely the Lüshi Chunqiu 吕氏春秋 and the Guanzi 管子. This second period also has provided us with two landmark Huang-Lao writings, namely the excavated Mawangdui Laozi 馬王堆老子, representing the first known complete editions of the Daodejing, albeit in their own Huang-Lao version that superseded Laozi's earlier Yangsheng version, at least for the lettered classes, as well as the Huangdi sijing 黄帝四经, the first collection of writings that reveal Huang-Lao thought in its full development. The third phase of Huang-Lao spans from the beginning of the Han Dynasty to the reign of Han Emperor Wu 漢武帝 (r. 141- 87BC). It was during this period that Huang-Lao enjoyed a dominant position in state ideology and the administration of government policy, in no small part due to its embrace by the a number of high-ranking officials, including Cao Shen 曹參 (d. 190 BCE) and his successor Chen Ping 陳平 (d. 178 BCE), as well as by the Han Emperors Wen 漢文帝 (r. 180 to 157 BC) and Jing 漢景帝 (r. 157 to 141 BC), whose commitment to Huang-Lao was strongly supported by Empress Dowager Dou 竇皇後 (d. 135 BC), wife of the former and mother of the latter. This period also saw the completion of the most sophisticated writings of the Huang-Lao tradition, including the Wenzi 文子, Heguanzi 鶡冠子, and Huainanzi 淮南子. This period came to a dramatic close with the death of Liu An 劉安, the Prince of Huainan (who was responsible for the Huainanzi), in 122 BC at the hands of Emperor Wu, who banished Huang-Lao from the court and replaced it with Confucian ideology and government policy. The final phase of Huang-Lao, from the middle of the Western Han to the end of the Eastern Han or shortly thereafter, is marked by the distance of its adherents from the centers of imperial power together with their desire to have Huang-Lao reinstated therein. This phase first comes to light with the semi-hermit Yan Zun 嚴遵 (fl. 83 B.C.E.-10 C.E.) and his complete edition of the Daodejing with an appended commentary, Laozi Zhigui 老子指歸, which lays out the full panoply of Huang-Lao cosmological and political concerns by

way of his commentary to the text. His work was soon followed by another Huang-Lao edition of and appended commentary to the Daodejing, Heshang Gong's Commentary to the Laozi 老子河上公章句, composed by an anonymous Huang-Lao scholar under the pseudonym of Heshang Gong 河上公; it was this work that served as the basic text that would become known to us as the received edition. Next to its Huang-Lao cosmology and political philosophy, another noteworthy feature of Heshang Gong's text is its prominent emphasis on popular religious practices that were believed to lead to immortality, which were sometimes identified with yangsheng practice, showing that, in this final stage of Huang-Lao Daoism, it led the way into the immortality practices of future movements of religious Daoism. Many of these trends can be seen in the biographies of Eastern Han personages, including those found in Han shu 漢書, Qian Han shu 前漢書, and Hou Han shu 後漢書, which commonly introduce their subjects as "loving Huang-Lao" 愛黃老, "cultivating Huang-Lao" 修黃老, and "practicing Huang-Lao techniques" 學黃老術. Already by the time of the Wei-Jin Dynasty, Huang-Lao had been displaced as the dominant Daoist tradition by Xuanxue Daoism 玄學道, with its philosophical appeal to the literati class, as well as by Tianshi Daoism 天師道, with its practical appeal to the popular masses.

Date Range: 476 BCE - 220 CE

Region: Han

Region tags: East Asia, Asia, China

Han

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Peerenboom, Randall P. 1993. *Law and Morality in Ancient China: The Silk Manuscripts of Huang-Lao*. New York: State University of New York Press.
- Source 2: Michael, Thomas. 2023. On the Fiercely Debated Questions of a Chinese Metaphysics and a Tradition of Early Daoism: Western and Chinese Perspectives on the Daodejing and Huang-Lao Daoism. *Religions* 14: 1- 23.
- Source 3: Ess, Hans van. 1993. The Meaning of Huang-Lao in Shiji and Hanshu. *Études chinoises* 12: 161-77.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/mawangdui>
- Source 1 Description: 馬王堆老子
- Source 2 URL: <https://ctext.org/huainanzi>
- Source 2 Description: 淮南子
- Source 3 URL: <https://ctext.org/wenzi>
- Source 3 Description: 文字
- Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/he-guan-zi>
- Source 1 Description: 鶡冠子
- Source 2 URL: <https://ctext.org/heshanggong>

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

— Yes

Notes: In Warring States period, in debates with other philosophical groups including Confucians, Legalists, and other Daoist groups. In Western Han, in interaction with other political factions. In Eastern Han, closely aligned with groups of religious Daoists.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

— No

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

— No

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

— No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

— No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

— No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

— No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

— Field doesn't know

Does the religion have official political support

— Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

— No

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Yes

Notes: This is the case when Huang-Lao was dominant court ideology in Western Han.

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: From the Warring States to the end of the Han Dynasty, their numbers were likely in the thousands.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (unknown relationship to other religious groups, or presence of other religious groups unknown)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In terms of Huang-Lao lineages, there were recognized leaders serving as masters to their disciples. Once Huang-Lao became embedded in the political structure of the Western Han, its recognized leader was the emperor, specifically Emperors Wen and Jing.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– No

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: There were many important texts, but the Daodejing was held as canonical beyond all others.

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: Based on the title "Huang-Lao," the two central figures were Huangdi and Laozi, neither were taken as supernatural but both were the subject of legends.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– Yes

Notes: In theory, the Daodejing was not open to alteration, but in actuality Huang-Lao adherents had subtly altered the original text in numerous ways.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: As described in the Shiji 史記 (Records of the Grand Historian), Huang-Lao masters transmitted the texts and teachings to their disciples.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Only the Daodejing was considered canonical, none of their other important writings achieved this status.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Field doesn't know

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Laozi's pre-Huang-Lao version of the Daodejing does not clearly describe any radical split between mind or spirit and body. Indeed, his understanding of human life appears to require the constant binding of spirit and body, and the kinds of practices that he advocates, generally under the category of what would be recognized as yangsheng, are focused on revitalizing both mind and spirit in tandem with each other. This dramatically changes with the development of Huang-Lao thought and practice, which relegated yangsheng practices (including breath circulation, calisthenics, sexual arts, and special diets called "avoiding grains") to a secondary position as they prioritized a form of spiritual concentration called zuowang performed in meditative immobility, which they absorbed from the Neiye and Zhuangzi. The intent was to release the spirit from the body to achieve a spiritual union with the Dao; this marks one of the defining differences between Laozi's Daoism and Huang-Lao Daoism. From its earliest formation, however, Huang-Lao thought was centered on the sage-king who, by way of this mystical union with the Dao, was enabled to know the cosmic principles of the Dao and

implement them in his government.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– No

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Field doesn't know

Belief in afterlife:

– No

Notes: This would likely not be different from the common ancestral offerings and worship.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Field doesn't know

Are grave goods present:

– Field doesn't know

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– No

Notes: At least not outside of traditional beliefs in natural spirits, but even so, recognition of supernatural beings in the Huang-Lao writings, particularly the voluminous Huainanzi and the Guanzi, often have little to do with active beliefs or practices directed to them and are situated in a

mythological context of general cosmology where they serve symbolic or rhetorical purposes. Huang-Lao writings also mention Tian 天 (Heaven), a power that was widely recognized as the (semi-anthropomorphic) celestial moral authority of the world in non-Daoist writings, but in the hands of Huang-Lao, it was thoroughly naturalized as simply the sky, and it was often coupled with Di 地 (earth) as providing the limits of the world. It should go without saying that the foundational notion of Daoism, namely the Constant Dao (常道 changdao) was the very source of heaven and earth and all things and beings in it, but it was systematically presented in virtually all Daoist philosophical writings as without any intention, design, or teleology.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Strongly present and highlighted

Notes: This distinction is basic to most forms of Daoist philosophy.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– Yes

Notes: They are linked to the Constant Dao and its cosmic principles that ought to be embodied.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– Only specialized religious class

Notes: To Huang-Lao adherents.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Particularly those identified with yin 陰 but not those identified with yang 陽. For most all of the specific virtues listed and queried under "Additional Questions" herein, Laozi's Daodejing in fact has much to say about them in its own semi-paradoxical manner, but they are downplayed in Huang-Lao writings, which tend to prioritize statecraft in the hands of the sage-ruler over the personal ethics of individuals. This is to say that these virtues apply to the king and his governing of the empire first of all. Furthermore and for example, Daoist philosophy in general has its own code of ethics that appears to

disparage specific ethics valued by Confucianism since they are seen as artificial, which goes against the spontaneous exercise of natural goodness, with particular value placed on a kind of absorptive empathy for the life experience of the common people, prior to its being put into definitional language of assessment, as often found in Confucian writings.

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– No

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– No

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– No

↳ Generosity / charity:

– No

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– No

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– No

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– No

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– No

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– No

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– No

- ↳ Cooperation:
 - No
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - No
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - No
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - No
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - No
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - No
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - No
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - No
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - No
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - No
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - No

- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - No
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - No
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - No
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - No
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - No
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - No
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Notes: Dynasty rather than empire.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: Huang-Lao masters would certainly have been cared for by their disciples.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Within the scope of the master-disciple transmissions of the teachings.

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: They populated the formal bureaucracy during the Western Han.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– No

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No